

Correlation between Artificial Intelligence on Mental Health and Retention Skills among Undergraduate Students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

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Abstract

This study investigated the correlation between artificial intelligence on mental health and retention skills among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. Two objectives, 2 research questions and 2 hypotheses were formulated for the study. The study adopted descriptive survey type of research design. The population of the study comprises of 100 to 400 level undergraduate students of Computer Science, Faculty of Computer Science & Artificial Intelligence, Federal University of Dutsin-Ma during the 2023/2024 academic session. Simple random sampling technique was used to select the level of the respondents while purposive sampling technique was used to select 300 (165 male and 135 female) students selected from the target population using Multistage sampling technique. Three instruments were used for the data collection namely Artificial Intelligence Scale (AIS), Mental Health Scale (MHS) and Retention Skills Scale (RSS), they were subjected to reliability test and Pearson Moment Correlation Statistics was used to determine the reliability coefficients as follows reliability coefficient of 0.70, 0.68 and 0.70 respectively, were obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient reliability test. The finding revealed that there was a significant relationship between Artificial Intelligence, Mental Health and students' retention skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina. The study concludes that artificial intelligence has significant correlation between mental health and students' retention skills. The findings recommended among others that higher institutions of learning should provide adequate training and support to students and lecturers to ensure they are proficient in using Artificial Intelligence technologies effectively.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Mental Health, Retention Skills and Undergraduates

Introduction

The impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on mental health, human behavior, and overall well-being is a complex and continuously evolving issue. As the field of artificial intelligence (AI) progresses, it becomes imperative to achieve a delicate equilibrium between leveraging its advantageous capabilities for mental health assistance and confronting the obstacles it presents in terms of human conduct and privacy.

The advent of artificial intelligence (AI) has presented itself as an innovative technology that holds the capacity to bring about significant transformations in multiple domains of human existence, encompassing mental well-being. The convergence of AI and mental health is a captivating field of study that has a multitude of prospects for enhancing the identification, intervention, and holistic welfare of those grappling with mental health difficulties. One of the foremost benefits of AI in the field of mental health is in its capacity to identify and forecast mental disorders during their nascent phases. Through the examination of extensive amounts of data, encompassing social media posts, internet behaviors, and physiological measurements, AI systems possess the capability to discern nuanced patterns and indicators linked to diverse mental diseases (Torous et al, 2021).

The domains of mental health and artificial intelligence (AI) are undergoing rapid advancements, exhibiting the capacity to mutually influence one another in significant ways. The increasing prevalence of mental health illnesses has prompted the exploration of potential remedies in the field of AI, which show promise in the areas of early detection, prevention, and therapy (Koki, 2023). Mental health is a term that is used in human development field. The individual and the environment play a role in one's overall wellbeing, especially early childhood and adolescence. It is commonly

acknowledged that family and environment is significant for effective growth of the individual. Mental health is usually conceptualized as combination of positive emotional states such as happiness and functioning with optimal effectiveness in individual's social life (Lee & Torous, 2021). In the study of Odeleye (2019), mental health is about lives going well and it is the combination of feeling good and functioning well. Mental health issues continue to be a global concern, with a steady 13% prevalence over the past 10 years and a statistical projection that nearly one in four people worldwide will be affected by a mental or neurological disorder at some point in their lives (Batada & Solano, 2019) Despite this prevalence, mental health remains a largely overlooked aspect of global health, with disparities in access, quality, and care affordability. It therefore means that people with high mental health feel happy, capable, well supported, and satisfied with life. Additionally, mental health describes the degree to which individuals believe they have real influence over their lives and their activities.

Retention is the ability of students to consistently remain and progress in school until the completion of the educational cycle (Bawa, 2019). It means a student on a given grade level remains and progresses to the next, session by session through the completion of the educational cycle. School curriculum contents are arranged sequentially and progressively on the building blocks of knowledge acquisition as the child progresses. If a child stays out of school, she/he will be deprived of the cumulative knowledge and skills that are supposed to be acquired to justify that level of education through the modular learning of the curriculum (Bawa, 2019). Retention in the successful completion of students' academic goals attainment or students meeting clearly defined educational goals whether career advancement or achievement of new skills (Ismail, 2017). Therefore, it as a result of the above gap that this study seeks to impact of artificial intelligence on undergraduate students' mental health and retention skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State.

With the improvement of science and technology, there has been a drastic spread in the various aspects of information technology in the heart of the society. The impact of such a sector has improved the notions of data automation and data analysis. Artificial Intelligence (AI), Cloud Computing, Big Data and similar others have improved the quality of life. Artificial intelligence helps by developing different software applications for improving the quality of the education system. Artificial intelligence helps the students by giving answers to all the queries that have been asked by the students at any time of the day (Chen, 2020).

It is currently difficult to completely understand the impacts of AI in higher education; hence more studies should be done to widen the understanding of this topic and create a wider platform for informed debate. The authors have discussed the challenges facing the adoption of AI in higher learning and the possible solutions (Reese, 2019). However, the adoption of AI in higher education is still at its earliest stages; therefore, only a few research studies have been done empirically. It is on this basis that this study finds it necessary to investigate the correlation between Artificial Intelligence on Undergraduate Students' Mental Health and Retention Skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to determine the correlation between artificial intelligence on mental health and retention skills among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. Specifically, to:

1. Find out the impact of artificial intelligence on mental health among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State
2. Investigate the impact of artificial intelligence on retention skills among Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State
3. Examine the relationship between artificial intelligence and mental health among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State
4. Examine the relationship between artificial intelligence and retention skills among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the conduct of this study:

1. What is impact of artificial intelligence on mental health among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State?
2. What is the impact of artificial intelligence on retention skills among Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested in the study.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence and mental health among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence and retention skills among Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive survey research design. Specifically, of correlational research type. This type of study seeks to establish what relationship exists between two or more variables. Usually, such studies indicate the direction and magnitude of the relationship between the variables. The population of the study comprised of 100 to 400 level of Computer Science of the Faculty of Computer and Artificial Intelligence, Federal University of Dutsin-Ma. Purposive random sampling technique was used to select 300 level and 400 level undergraduate students. The simple random sampling technique was used to select 150 among 300 level students and 150 students among 400 level students making 300 (165 male and 135 female) respondents for the study. Three instruments were used for data collection. These are: Artificial Intelligence Scale (AIS), Mental Health Scale (MHS) and Retention Skills Scale (RSS) which were subjected to test re- test method and Pearson Moment Correlation Statistics was used to determine the reliability coefficients which yielded 0.70, 0.68 and 0.70. Each of the three scales has 10 items with 4 points scale ranging from Strongly Disagree (1), to Disagree (2), Agree (3) and Strongly Agree (4). The research questions 1 and were answered using mean and standard deviation Also, the research hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) Statistic at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Research Question One:

What is impact of artificial intelligence on mental health among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State?

Table 1: Showing the mean and standard deviation of impact of artificial intelligence on mental health among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Decision
Artificial Intelligence	300	9.03	2.01	Positive
Students' Retention Skills	300	10.44	1.60	

Table 1 revealed the impact of Artificial Intelligence on Undergraduate Students' Mental Health in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. It showed that mean score of Artificial Intelligence was 9.03 and Students' Mental Health mean score was 10.44. This means that artificial intelligence has positive impact on Undergraduate Students' Mental Health in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Research Question Two:

What is the impact of artificial intelligence on retention skills among Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State?

Table 2: Showing mean and standard deviation of impact of artificial intelligence on retention skills among Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Decision
Artificial Intelligence	300	9.36	1.20	Positive
Students' Retention Skills	300	9.39	1.47	

Table 2 revealed the impact of Artificial Intelligence on Undergraduate Students' Retention Skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. It showed that mean score of Artificial Intelligence was (9.36) and Students' Retention Skills mean score was (9.39). This means that artificial intelligence has positive impact on Undergraduate Students' Retention Skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Testing of Hypotheses

H₀₁:

There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence and mental health among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Table 3: Table showing the Correlation analysis between artificial intelligence and mental health among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	Cal Value	.r-	Critical r-value	Decision
Artificial Intelligence	300	22.65	10.75	298	0.38	.21	0.21	Accepted
Students' Mental Health	300	23.46	11.43					

P<0.05

Table 3 revealed that the calculated r-value is (0.38) is greater than the Critical r-value (0. 21) at 0.05 level of significance and 298 degrees of freedom. Hence, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This implies that there was a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and undergraduate students' mental health in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

HO₂:

There is no significant relationship between artificial intelligence and retention skills among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Table4: Showing Correlation analysis between artificial intelligence and retention skills among undergraduate students in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	Cal Value	.r-	Critical r-value	Decision
Artificial Intelligence	300	21.96	11.77	298	0.63	.32	0.32	Accepted
Retention Skills	300	43.86	12.33					

P>0.05

Table 4 revealed that the calculated r-value (0.63) is greater than the Critical r-value (0. 32) at 0.05 level of significance and 298 degree of freedom. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. This implies that there was a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and undergraduate students' retention skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State

Summary of finding

This study examined impact of Artificial Intelligence on Undergraduate Students' Mental Health and Retention Skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. Thus, the finding of this study was summarized as follows;

1. The study indicated that artificial intelligence (mean score 9.03) has positive impact on Undergraduate Students' Mental Health (mean score 10.44) in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State
2. The study revealed that artificial intelligence (mean score 9.36)) has positive impact on Undergraduate Students' retention skills (mean score 9.39) in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State
3. There was a significant relationship between Artificial Intelligence and Undergraduate Students' Mental Health in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State (calculated r-value (0.38) >Critical r-value 0.21) at 0.05 level of significance
4. There was a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and undergraduate students' retention skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State (calculated r-value 0.63 >Critical r-value 0. 32) at 0.05 level of significance

Discussions of Findings

Research question one indicated that artificial intelligence has positive impact on Undergraduate Students' Mental Health in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. The finding of this study corroborates with Patra, Sethia, and Gupta, (2018) found that the moderate uses of artificial intelligence (AI) enhance Mental Health as a result of prevention of high level of stress.

Research question two revealed that artificial intelligence has positive impact on Undergraduate Students' retention skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. The finding of this study agrees with Kim and. Kim (2022) who found that the uses of artificial intelligence influences and enhances students' retention skills and learning outcome.

The result of hypothesis one revealed that there was a significant relationship between Artificial Intelligence and Undergraduate Students' Mental Health in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. The finding of this study agrees with Patra, Sethia, and Gupta (2018) who found that there was significant relationship between Artificial Intelligence and Undergraduate Students' Mental Health and the moderate uses of artificial intelligence (AI) enhances mental health because it prevents high level of stress.

The result of hypothesis two showed that there was a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and undergraduate students' retention skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State. The finding of this study corroborates with Kim and Kim (2022) who found that there exists a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and undergraduate students' retention skills. It further found that the uses of artificial intelligence influences and enhances students' retention skills and learning outcome.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the followings were the conclusions. The findings of this study concluded that the level of artificial intelligence utilization among Undergraduate Students was moderate this means that students do not experience negative mental health as a result of utilization of artificial intelligence, the level of mental health was moderate, that the level of students' retention skills was high, Artificial intelligence has positive impact on Undergraduate Students' Mental Health, Artificial intelligence has positive impact on Undergraduate Students' retention skills. Also, there was a significant relationship between Artificial Intelligence and Undergraduate Students' Mental Health and there was a significant relationship between artificial intelligence and undergraduate students' retention skills in Federal University Dutsin-Ma, Katsina State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Higher institutions of learning should provide adequate training and support to students and lecturers to ensure they are proficient in using AI technologies effectively.
2. AI tools should be made more accessible and user-friendly to encourage increased utilization.
3. Universities and other higher Institutions of learning should establish mechanisms to monitor and evaluate the impact of AI tools on student' retention skills, learning outcomes, collecting data on variables such as student engagement, satisfaction, and performance.
4. Universities and other higher Institutions of learning should ensure that AI utilization by undergraduate students is not abuse in such a way that could affect their mental health negatively.

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